

**RISK ANALYSIS OF HEAT WAVES
AND THEIR IMPACT ON VULNERABLE
GROUPS IN HUÉRCAL-OVERA**

LUGIA PROJECT

AUGUST 2025

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents the findings from the initial phase of the LUGIA project, conducted in the municipality of Huércal-Overa (Almería). The main objective was to analyze the impacts of climate change—particularly heat waves—and to assess the related risks affecting the local population, economy, and natural environment. Utilizing CLIMAAX tools adapted for the local context, the study was enhanced with specific methodologies designed to provide a more accurate characterization of climate exposure and vulnerability.

Territorial, natural and socioeconomic context

Huércal-Overa, in Almería's Levante region, has a semi-arid Mediterranean climate with hot, dry summers and relies heavily on agriculture and livestock. Over 70% of its residents live in the main urban center within a landscape dominated by scrubland-grassland, limited forests, and the Estancias and Almagro mountain ranges. Sparse vegetation reduces thermal regulation and heightens heat exposure.

Huércal-Overa has just over 20,000 residents, a relatively young demographic but with an increasing percentage over 65 (12%). Foreigners make up 20% of the population. The economy is mainly driven by agriculture, pig farming, and services. Average gross income is about €22,300, while unemployment exceeds the national rate. These socioeconomic factors affect the community's climate vulnerability and ability to handle extreme events.

Climate analysis: trends and projections

Historical analysis indicates a warming trend in Huércal-Overa. In the past 50 years, the average temperature has increased by over 1°C, reaching

19.2°C in 2024. The number of warm days ($\geq 30^\circ\text{C}$) and tropical nights has doubled, while rainfall has decreased and become more irregular, with a record low observed in 2024 (100.9 mm). These patterns are consistent with global climate projections and suggest that the municipality is experiencing significant changes in its climate characteristics.

Projections using CLIMAAX tools (Workflows 1 and 2) indicate that the number of heatwave days could rise by anywhere from 100% to 600% by 2075, depending on the emissions scenario (RCP 4.5 versus RCP 8.5). The Rothfusz Heat Index suggests that, although critical thresholds for heat stress may not be surpassed, the area is likely to experience consistently high levels of heat stress and exhaustion among the population. The Heat-Wave Index supports these findings, showing that under the RCP 8.5 scenario, Huércal-Overa may face more than 20 heatwave days per year by 2040, with notable consequences for public health, energy demand, and economic productivity.

Climate Risk Assessment

Satellite data (Workflow 3) and climate projections (Workflow 4) indicate that climate risk is predominantly concentrated within the urban centre of Huércal-Overa, with notable vulnerability in the northern, southern, and central-eastern sectors of the municipality. These regions are characterised by a high density of at-risk populations, including children and older adults, compounded by surface overheating and limited vegetation cover. The resulting risk maps enable the targeted identification of critical areas where interventions should be prioritised.

Integration of demographic sources (WorldPop and INE) corroborates that Huércal-Overa town is the principal locus of climate risk. Census data further

refine this estimate, highlighting elevated vulnerability along the north-south axis and surrounding key sites such as Adolfo Suárez Municipal Park, the employment office, and the Hospital de la Inmaculada. Incorporating vegetation analysis affirms the important regulatory role of urban green infrastructure, thus identifying priority zones where climate risk coincides with insufficient vegetation coverage.

General Conclusions

The project demonstrates that Huércal-Overa faces an urgent challenge posed by climate change, notably with increasing heatwave risks impacting public health, urban quality of life, and the local economy. The convergence of risk in densely populated urban districts with minimal green spaces underscores the necessity for nature-based adaptation strategies, integrated within territorial and urban planning frameworks.

Enhancing and expanding green infrastructure—by increasing tree planting, permeable surfaces, and shaded areas—is recommended as a crucial intervention to mitigate temperatures, improve thermal comfort, and support long-term resilience. Additionally, incorporating socioeconomic and health variables in subsequent phases will facilitate the development of a comprehensive vulnerability index, thereby enabling more targeted public policy responses.

The findings generated in this initial phase provide a robust scientific foundation for local climate action, presenting clear evidence of both the urgency for intervention and the specific locations where resources should be allocated. Huércal-Overa is thereby positioned to serve as a model municipality in climate adaptation, translating scientific evidence into practical, sustainable measures to safeguard its population and enhance resilience to climate change.

INTRODUCTION

Urban heat: A global risk with local effects

According to NASA data, **the average global temperature has increased by approximately 2 degrees Fahrenheit (about 1°C) since the end of the 19th century¹**. Notably, this warming trend has not been uniform; rather, it has accelerated in recent decades. The seven warmest years on record have all occurred since 2015, highlighting the rapid intensification of global temperatures. Specifically, **2023 was among the warmest years recorded, with 2024 surpassing that benchmark by exceeding 1.5°C of warming relative to pre-industrial levels for several consecutive months²**.

The trend of rising global temperatures is widely supported by robust scientific evidence and has heightened concern across various societal sectors. Institutions, businesses, and citizens acknowledge that extreme weather events represent one of the principal threats to future stability. This consensus is particularly evident when considering medium-term risks, establishing climate change as the most urgent challenge over the next decade³.

Current scientific projections suggest that by 2030, the critical threshold of **1.5°C of global warming above pre-industrial levels** may be reached. Surpassing this threshold would jeopardize vulnerable ecosystems worldwide and directly affect regions already under climatic stress, such as **Levante Almería**.

In municipalities like **Huércal-Overa**, where a semi-arid climate and water scarcity influence local and urban dynamics, accelerated warming poses the risk of further degradation to local ecosystems. Both native vegetation and agricultural systems dependent on climatic stability may be adversely impacted. Probable scenarios include reduced biodiversity, loss of plant cover, and disruption of local hydrological balance.

Climate Risks: Impacts on Health and Economy

Moreover, climate change is anticipated to trigger additional negative socio-environmental outcomes, particularly in urban areas. In Huércal-Overa, the combination of elevated temperatures and limited green spaces amplifies residents' exposure to **heat waves** and reduces thermal comfort, thereby increasing risks to public health, especially among the most vulnerable groups.

It is estimated that one in four deaths can be attributed to preventable environmental causes⁴, including those related to heat, extreme weather events, the proliferation of infectious diseases, or exacerbation of chronic illnesses. Prolonged heat waves are directly linked to increased hospitalizations (by 3% to 8%), chiefly affecting metabolic and obesity-related conditions. Additional environmental factors inherent to urban settings, such as air pollution, can further aggravate these heat-related effects⁵. Related research also suggests an average **15.3% rise in acute cardiovascular incidents** during heat waves among adults aged 40–75, with higher impacts observed among men and vulnerable populations. These findings underline emerging evidence that social inequalities may amplify the projected health impacts in urban environments⁶.

Data from the MoMo (Daily Mortality Monitoring, Carlos III Health Institute) indicates that during the summer of 2024 (May 15 to September 30), the province of Almería experienced 40 excess deaths attributable to high temperatures, predominantly affecting individuals over 65 years old and women⁷.

Under a 2-degree warming scenario, **an additional 1.4 billion people will be exposed to heat stress⁸**, with many experiencing its most severe consequences. As a result, public health must remain central to climate policy, given projections that **direct health costs**—excluding agriculture,

water, and sanitation—will reach **US\$2 billion to US\$4 billion per year by 2030**⁹.

Beyond quality of life and health, economic growth is also being affected by rising global temperatures. Between 1992 and 2013, **the global economic impact of heat waves resulted in losses ranging from US\$5 trillion to US\$29.3 trillion**, accounting for up to 6.7% of GDP per capita in low-income economies and 1.5% in high-income regions¹⁰. Anticipated costs are expected to rise with continued warming, with economic losses due to heat stress projected to total \$2.4 trillion by 2030¹¹. A single significant extreme weather event can reduce GDP by approximately 0.2%¹², indicating these phenomena exert a more pronounced long-term economic effect than average changes, though they may not necessarily alter overall economic growth rates.

Even under the most favorable scenarios (not exceeding 1.5°C warming and conducting outdoor labor in shaded conditions), it is projected that **2.2% of global working hours will be lost by 2030** due to heat. Considering critical sectors such as agriculture and livestock—central to Huércal-Overa's economy—where much work takes place outdoors, lost working hours could rise to 3.8% globally by 2030, equivalent to 136 million jobs¹³.

Huércal-Overa Confronts the Climate Challenge

In summary, the case of Huércal-Overa illustrates how climate change is evolving from an abstract concept into a **tangible challenge directly impacting health, well-being, and the local economy**. In a region already affected by aridity, water scarcity, and ecosystem fragility, ongoing warming and increasingly frequent extreme events, such as heat waves, present growing risks—particularly for the most vulnerable populations and the most exposed economic sectors, like agriculture.

Given these realities, there is an urgent need for **territorial and urban planning grounded in scientific evidence and climate adaptation strategies** to anticipate impacts and enhance local resilience.

SCOPE OF WORK

LUGIA was established with the objective of analysing future climate scenarios anticipated for the municipality of Huércal-Overa and evaluating the risks that extreme heat may pose to public health, with particular focus on vulnerable populations. The project is dedicated to the strategic application of vegetation as an intelligent approach to climate adaptation, promoting the implementation of nature-based solutions that mitigate the effects of heat waves and position the municipality as a leader in climate resilience.

During this initial phase, a comprehensive study of climate projections for the region is conducted, identifying the principal climate risks projected to impact the municipality in the coming decades. The project utilises CLIMAAX tools, complemented by methodological refinements tailored to the specific environmental, urban, and socio-economic context of Huércal-Overa.

The objectives for this first phase, related to the application of CLIMAAX tools, include:

- **Analysis of future climate scenarios** in Huércal-Overa, with a particular emphasis on heat waves, aimed at estimating critical parameters such as frequency, duration, and intensity.
- **Assessment of health and well-being risks** associated with these projected climate scenarios, with special consideration for the most vulnerable groups within the population.

Additionally, a third objective, though not directly tied to the use of these tools but essential for subsequent phases, is included:

- **Initial identification of relevant stakeholders** in the LUGIA project, to recognize key entities, groups, and individuals potentially affected by climate change impacts or capable of influencing the design, implementation, and sustainability of proposed solutions.

This first phase serves as a foundational step in developing a robust local climate adaptation strategy, grounded in scientific evidence and a multisectoral perspective. By integrating specific climate data, health and territorial risk assessments, and stakeholder mapping, this initiative will enable the creation of a realistic, participatory, and effective roadmap, establishing Huércal-Overa as a model municipality equipped to address the challenges posed by climate change.

GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT HUÉRCAL-OVERA

4.1. Territorial context

Huércal-Overa is a town in Almería, Andalusia, Spain. It borders several municipalities in both Almería and Murcia provinces. The area is divided into eight population entities—six are provincial councils—covering thirty-nine centres, including Huércal-Overa, Santa María de Nieva, El Saltador, San Francisco, Úrcal, La Atalaya, and Las Minas.

Huércal-Overa is situated 104 kilometres from Almería, 113 kilometres from Murcia, and 191 kilometres from Granada. Its coordinates are 37°23'24"N, 1°56'37"W based on the ETRS89 geodetic system. The municipality encompasses a surface area of 318.04 km² and reaches a maximum elevation of 1,247 metres at Cabezo de la Jara. Major transportation routes include the Mediterranean Highway (A-7), which links Almería and Murcia, the

Figure 4.1. Main population centers in the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: SIOSE AR 2016. Prepared by the authors.

N-340 national road, as well as regional highways A-327 (towards Vélez-Rubio), A-334 (to Albox), and A-350 (to Pulpi)¹⁴.

The topography of Huércal-Overa is defined by three primary units: the Almanzora River valley to the south, the Almagro mountain range to the east, and a northern mountainous sector forming part of the foothills of the Estancias mountain range. Elevation within the municipality varies from 1,247 metres at Cabezo de la Jara, located on the provincial border with Murcia, to 180 metres at the Cuevas del Almanzora reservoir. The town centre is positioned at an altitude of 280 metres above sea level.

The Almagro mountain range, an extension of the Betic Mountain Range, spans the municipalities of Huércal-Overa and Cuevas del Almanzora, serving as a natural boundary between these territories.

The highest point in this range is Cucharón, at 714 metres, and its northern plateau accommodates the town of Huércal-Overa. The Almanzora River traverses the Almagro range, flowing northwest to southeast until it reaches the Cuevas de Almanzora reservoir¹⁵.

To the north, the Estancias mountain range delineates the border between Almería and Murcia, attaining the municipality's highest elevation at Cabezo de la Jara (1,247 metres). The Almanzora River, extending 110 kilometres with a basin of 2,611 km², is among Andalusia's principal Mediterranean waterways. Within the municipal territory, it passes near the districts of Los Navarros and Las Menas, ultimately joining the Cuevas de Almanzora reservoir on the southeastern boundary.

In Huércal-Overa, most of the area is non-urbanizable agricultural land used mainly for farming

Figure 4.2. Topographic map of the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: SIOSE AR 2016. Prepared by the authors.

Figure 4.3. Land use map of the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: SIOSE AR 2016. Prepared by the authors.

Table 4.1. Land uses in the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: SIOSE AR 2016. Prepared by the authors.

Land uses

Type	Surface (ha)	Surface (%)
Crops	14,709.915	46.25
Scrubland areas	11,890.1	37.38
Wooded areas (conifers, broadleaves)	2,274.046	7.15
Road network	816.745	2.57
Artificial	762.709	2.40
River channels and systems	693.51	2.8
Open areas with little vegetation	659.639	2.07

and livestock. Key uses are fruit and citrus orchards as well as arable crops, which are central to the local economy base.

In Huércal-Overa, agriculture dominates land use: crops make up 46.25% and scrub-grassland 37.38%, totalling 83.63% of the area. Forests cover just 7.15%. Human-made areas along roads (2.57%) and in urban centres (2.40%) account for 4.97%. Riverbeds, including the Almanzora River and Cuevas de Almanzora Reservoir, occupy 2.18%, while sparsely vegetated zones—mainly vacant transitional spaces—comprise 2.07%.

4.2. Natural context

The municipality of Huércal-Overa encompasses a natural environment of significant ecological importance, defined by the foothills of the Estancias and Almagro mountain ranges, the Almanzora River, and a pervasive presence of agricultural activity.

Within the municipality, **four primary series of potential vegetation**¹⁶ have been identified. These ecological units reflect the natural succession of plant communities and provide the framework for landscape classification in the region. The following describes each series found within the territory:

- **24th: Supra-meso-Mediterranean Filabric and Silicolous Nevadan Series – Holm Oak (*Quercus rotundifolia*)**¹⁷. This series is characteristic of mountainous areas with clayey soils, where

dense holm oak forests with substantial layers of thorny shrubs predominate. Plant communities here include holm oak stands, thornbush thickets, and broom formations featuring species such as holm oak (*Quercus rotundifolia*), yellow broom (*Retama sphaerocarpa*), and barberry (*Berberis hispanica*). It is primarily distributed across the Sierra de las Estancias, specifically in the upper northern foothills of the municipality.

- **29a: Mesomediterranean Series of Murcian-Almerian, Guadiciano-Bacense, Setabense, Valencian-Tarraconensian, and Aragonese Semi-arid Regions – Kermes Oak (*Quercus coccifera*)**¹⁸. This series typifies Mediterranean arid zones with open communities including pine–kermes oak woodlands, broom–scobony thickets, and esparto grasslands. Representative species comprise Aleppo pine (*Pinus halepensis*), blackthorn (*Rhamnus lycioides*), and maritime grape (*Ephedra fragilis*). It accompanies the 24th series in the Sierra de las Estancias, marking the lower margins of the mountain area.
- **31a: Thermomediterranean Murcian-Almerian. Semi-arid Series – Mastic Tree (*Pistacia lentiscus*) (*Chamaeropo–Rhamneto lycioidis sigmetum*)**¹⁹. Representative of the semi-arid landscapes characteristic of the Murcia–Almería region, this series features thermophilous sclerophyllous shrublands. Dominant plant communities include bushes, brooms, and esparto grasses, with key species such as mastic tree (*Pistacia lentiscus*), blackthorn (*Rhamnus*

Table 4.2. Natural surfaces of the municipality. Source: Spanish Forest Map (MFE), Natura 2000 Network, Vegetation Series Map of the Peninsula and the Balearic Islands, and the General Network of Livestock Trails of Spain (RGVP). Prepared by the authors.

Natural environment

Type	Surface (ha)	Surface (%)
Red Natura 2000	1,060.81	3.34
Pine forests	1,591.4766	5.00
Mixture of conifers and hardwoods	131.6679	0.41
Holm oak forests	203.6772	0.64
Eucalyptus forests	25.7229	0.08
Oleaster groves	11.602	0.04
Scrubland - grassland	12,094.0416	38.03

Figure 4.4. Map of the natural environment of the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: Spanish Forest Map (MFE), Natura 2000 Network, Vegetation Series Map of the Peninsula and the Balearic Islands, and the General Network of Livestock Trails of Spain (RGVP). Prepared by the authors.

lycioides), palm heart (*Chamaerops humilis*), and broom (*Retama sphaerocarpa*). It occupies the lower basin areas with gentle topography, supporting much of the municipality's agricultural activity and the Almagro mountain range.

- **32b: Murcia–Almería Semi-arid to Arid Thermomediterranean Series – Jujube (*Ziziphus lotus*)²⁰.** Also prevalent within the semi-arid Murcia–Almería region, this series is characterized by scrub–grassland systems such as esparto grasslands, jujube fields, and thyme stands. Notable species include jujube (*Ziziphus lotus*), esparto grass (*Stipa tenacissima*), and cat's tail (*Sideritis laevigata*). This vegetation type is predominantly situated in the southern sector of the municipality, inclusive of the environs bordering the Almanzora River.

The municipality is predominantly characterized by scrublands and grasslands—specifically

sclerophyllous vegetation (38.03%) typical of Mediterranean environments²¹.

These areas are mainly situated in the foothills of the Sierra de las Estancias and in the southern sector of the municipality. Within these vegetation types, there exists a rich diversity of ecologically significant plant communities, including jujube forests, cornicales, and lentiscar forests. The salt marshes and gypsum deposits further enhance biodiversity through their notable endemic species, contributing to the ecological distinctiveness and environmental importance of the region.

Forested areas represent a relatively small proportion of municipal land (6.17%), comprising primarily pine forests located in the Almagro mountain range (5%). Holm oak forests can be found in the Estancias mountain range (0.64%), alongside reforested zones featuring broadleaf and coniferous

species situated both within this range and along the banks of the Almanzora River.

Overall, natural areas constitute 44.2% of the municipality's surface. Despite modifications largely attributable to agricultural activity, these regions retain considerable value due to their abundance of endemic species and the presence of conservation-worthy sites such as the Sierra de las Estancias, Sierra de Almagro, and the Almanzora River. The Almagro mountain²² range forms part of the Natura 2000 Network and has been designated a Special Area of Conservation (SAC), covering 3.34% of the municipality. Additional Natura 2000 sites near Huércal-Overa include the Cabezo de la Jara, the Rambla de Nogalte, and the Enmedio mountain range, all declared SAC zones²³.

The municipality also maintains 142.98 km of livestock trails, many of which originate within the town and connect to various points throughout the territory. Notably, the Cabrerías path spans 18.47 km, making it the longest livestock route in the area.

Regarding fauna²⁴, avian diversity includes species of particular relevance such as the golden eagle (*Aquila chrysaetos*), Bonelli's eagle (*Aquila fasciata*), and the eagle owl (*Bubo bubo*). Other notable birds comprise the trumpeter bullfinch (*Bucanetes githagineus*), stone-curlew (*Burhinus oedicephalus*), European roller (*Coracias garrulus*), and common lark (*Calandrella brachydactyla*). Among mammals, the cave bat (*Miniopterus schreibersii*), horseshoe bat (*Rhinolophus euryale*), and Moorish hedgehog (*Atelerix algirus*) are present. Amphibian species include the common toad (*Bufo bufo*), natterjack toad (*Epidalea calamita*), and common frog (*Pelophylax perezi*). Reptilian populations feature the Moorish tortoise (*Testudo graeca*), a vulnerable species requiring priority conservation efforts.

4.3. Sociodemographic Context

Huércal-Overa has a population of 20,575 residents, reflecting a growth trend of 4.47% since 2021 and 11.6% since 2011. Population distribution is concentrated, with 90.84% of inhabitants residing in urban centres and only 9.16% dispersed across rural areas. The principal population centre accounts for 14,805 residents, supplemented by

Table 4.3. Demographic data for the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: INE. Prepared by the authors. Year 2024.

Demographic data

Total population	20,575
Male population	10,251
Female population	10,324
Population in nuclei	18,691
Scattered population	1,884
Number of foreigners (2022)	4,251
Births (2023)	161
Deaths (2023)	189
Middle Ages	42.3
Percentage of population under 20 years old	21.7%
Percentage of population over 65 years of age	12.2%

La Molineta (460 inhabitants), La Atalaya (408 inhabitants), and Los Menas (386 inhabitants).

The average age is 42.3 years, which, while moderately high, remains below regional (Andalusian: 43.25 years) and national (Spanish: 44.37 years) averages. Foreign nationals number 4,251, representing 20.7% of the total population. The population pyramid presents a broad base (21.7% under 20 years) and a moderate peak (12.2% over 65 years).

Huércal-Overa has a higher proportion of children (0-14 years: 12.91%) than the national average (11.86%), likely due to higher birth rates or more young families. The population aged 65+ is lower (17.80% vs. 22.39% nationally), especially in the oldest age groups. The working-age group (15-64) makes up 69.29% locally, compared to 65.75% in Spain. The municipality has slightly more people aged 40-49, while Spain has more in the 50-64 bracket. Huércal-Overa also shows moderate population growth and a younger age structure, supported by a high migration rate (20.7%).

Huércal-Overa's urban growth centres on its main hub (14,805 residents), which expanded to absorb San Isidro. Nearby residential areas include La Molineta (460 residents), La Atalaya (408 residents), and smaller districts like Los Menas, El Pilar, and Santa María de Nieva. This setup results in a municipal population density of 41.48 inhabitants/ha, far above the national average of 0.97 inhabitants/ha²⁵ between the first quartile (27.9 inhabitants/ha) and

Figure 4.5. Population pyramid by sex and age (five-year groups) of the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: INE. Prepared by the authors. Year 2024.

Figure 4.6. Population census of the population centers of the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: Institute of Statistics and Cartography of Andalusia. Prepared by the authors. Year 2024.

the average (43 inhabitants/ha) of localities of its demographic size.

4.4. Economic context

In 2021, Huércal-Overa had 1,129 companies, with its economic structure primarily concentrated in the tertiary sector. Commerce accounted for 356 companies, logistics for 108, and hospitality for 110, reflecting the municipality's role as a regional hub. The primary sector maintained relevance with 280 companies, consistent with the area's agricultural and livestock activity, while construction included 168 companies linked to urban development.

Socioeconomic data indicate an average gross income of €22,343 (€18,765 available), a fiscal imbalance (income: €905 per inhabitant; expenses: €1,029 per inhabitant), and an unemployment rate of 13.5%, which is above the national average. Land registry records show more urban land (16,534 urban property tax receipts) compared to rural land (4,149 rural land receipts), indicating growth in the main population centre.

Agriculture and livestock are important in Huércal-Overa, especially citrus, almonds, and intensive pig farming—the municipality ranks seventh nationally. There are 18 fattening farms and 5 breeding farms, supported by local meat industries and changes in agricultural practices. The sector significantly affects employment and wealth, prompting the PGOU to establish an ordinance addressing environmental impacts²⁶. Agricultural land covers 46.25% of the area, mainly in the

Table 4.4. Economic activity and employment in the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: Andalusian Institute of Statistics and Cartography. Prepared by the authors. 2023.

Economic activity and employment	
Wholesale and retail trade	356
Agriculture, livestock, forestry and fishing	280
Construction	168
Hospitality	110
Transport and storage	108
Income and revenue	
Average gross income	22,343
Average disposable income	18,765
Income per capita	905
Expenditures per capita	1,029
Unemployment rate	13.50 %
Cadastral data	
Number of cadastral plots: Lots.	3,116
Urban property tax. Number of receipts	16,534
Rural property tax. Number of receipts	4,149

fertile central basin and near the main towns: Huércal-Overa, La Atalaya, El Saltador, and San Francisco.

In Huércal-Overa, woody crops dominate agriculture, covering 56.03% of farmland—mainly fruit trees (39.96%) like almonds, followed by citrus fruits (11.38%) and olive trees (4.69%). Herbaceous crops account for 1.71%, led by irrigated lettuce and dryland barley. Vineyards make up 0.41%, while greenhouse vegetables and fruits occupy

Table 4.5. Crop distribution. Source: Sigpac 2025. Prepared by the authors.

Cultivation areas

Type	Surface (ha)	Surface (%)
Olive trees	680.89	4.69
Citrus fruits	1,651.28	11.38
Fruit trees	5,800.22	39.96
Vegetables	248.65	1.71
Vineyards	59.21	0.41
Arable land	5,987.51	41.25
Greenhouses	88.71	0.61
Unproductive	1,168.02	8.05

Figure 4.7. Crop map in the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: Sigpac 2025. Prepared by the authors.

0.61%. Additionally, 41.25% of land is uncultivated arable, and 8.05% is unproductive.

In recent years, there has been an increase in greenhouses and unproductive areas, which has contributed to a reduction in arable and fruit-bearing land (SIGPAC 2017-2022). Nevertheless, non-intensive woody crop agriculture remains predominant in the municipality, accounting for 56.03% of agricultural activity.

Other Productive Sectors

Huércal-Overa demonstrates limited industrial development relative to neighboring municipalities such as Pulpí and Cuevas de Almanzora, a trend that is evident in various indicators including energy consumption by sector. However, it is important to highlight recent growth in the healthcare industry due to the establishment of new companies. Additionally, the construction sector continues to play a significant economic role, further supporting the local productive framework.

4.5. Climatic Context

Huércal-Overa is characterized by a Mediterranean climate with arid features. Summers are typically very hot and dry, while winters are mild, with occasional temperatures falling below 0 °C. The area experiences low but sometimes intense rainfall. Marked thermal contrasts and high levels of sunshine distinguish the municipality's climate. Within the **Köppen and Geiger climate classification**, Huércal-Overa is identified as having a semi-arid steppe climate (BSk). In Spain, this type of climate is generally found in Mediterranean regions exhibiting some continental characteristics, and is marked by severe summer droughts as well as grassland and sclerophyllous shrub vegetation, with sparse tree cover.

In Huércal-Overa, **prevailing wind patterns** are predominantly from the northwest (NW), followed in frequency by southwest (SW), south (S), and south-southwest (SSW) directions. Most winds range from 2 km/h to 20 km/h, with light winds

Huércal-Overa
 37.39°N, 1.94°W (285 m snm).
 Modelo: ERA5T.

Figure 4.8. Wind dynamics in the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: Meteoblue. Year 2024.

(2–5 km/h) being most frequent, and moderate winds (5–20 km/h) primarily coming from NW and SW directions. Notably, calm conditions (<2 km/h) are commonly observed across all wind directions. Winds originating from the east (ESE, SE), northeast (NE, NNE), and north (N) occur less frequently and typically at intensities lower than 5 km/h. Wind speeds exceeding 20 km/h are rare and generally occur in both the northeast (NE, ENE) and northwest (WNW, NW) sectors.

Below is a comprehensive historical study examining the climatic evolution of the municipality. For the recent period (2019–2024), annual data from the Huércal-Overa station, provided by AEMET, were utilized. Additionally, for the analysis of the historical series (1975–2020), information was sourced from the Platform on Adaptation to Climate Change in Spain (Adaptecca) of the Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Analysis of Climate Trends in Huércal-Overa During the Current Period (2019–2024)

Recent years in Huércal-Overa have been marked by an upward trend in temperatures and persistent drought conditions. The average annual

temperature increased by 1.0°C in 2024 compared to 2019, with consistent growth except for an anomaly in 2021 due to Storm Filomena. The frequency of warm days (temperature ≥30°C) has risen steadily, exceeding 90 consecutive days since 2022 and reaching a historical peak of 114 days, up from 78 days in 2019. Similarly, maximum temperatures have also escalated, remaining above an average of 25°C since 2022 and achieving a record daily high of 42.3°C in the summer of 2023. The occurrence of warm nights has progressively grown, surpassing 70 days annually since 2021 and maintaining this level through 2024.

Regarding precipitation, a notable reduction of 47% has been observed compared to 2019, declining from 210 mm per year to 100.9 mm in 2024. This decrease, although gradual with a minor rebound in 2021, does not reflect significant changes in the number of rainy days, which has remained stable without discernible trends. Thus, the reduced precipitation volume indicates a decline in rainfall intensity rather than changes in frequency or seasonality.

Figure 4.9. Climate trends over the past 5 years (2019-2024) in the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: AEMET. Prepared by the authors.

Analysis of climate trends in Huércal-Overa during the historical series (1975-2020)

The average temperature in Huércal-Overa has shown periodic fluctuations over the past 50 years. The highest recorded average temperature was 18.85°C in 1994, while the lowest was 16.66°C in 2010. During this period, the average temperature generally ranged between 17°C and 18°C. In comparison, the AEMET station reported an average temperature of 19.2°C for 2024, indicating an increase.

The graph of maximum temperatures closely mirrors average temperature trends, with a high of 24.89°C in 1994 and a low of 22.51°C in 2010. Most values range between 23°C and 24°C, but 2024 saw a record maximum of 25.2°C.

There is significant variability in the historical trend regarding the number of **warm days**. The highest value was recorded in 2015 with 66 warm days, while the lowest occurred in 1981 with just 6 days, representing a fluctuation of 60 days between these two extremes. Historically, the

Figure 4.10. Historical average temperature in the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: Adaptecca.

Figure 4.11. Historical average maximum temperatures in the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: Adaptecca.

Figure 4.12. Historical number of warm days in the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: Adaptecca.

average has ranged between 35 and 45 warm days; however, since the 2000s, there has been a notable increase in the average number of warm days, including within the lower values. In 2022, a maximum of 114 warm days was observed, and in 2024 that figure reached 92, both considerably higher than previous historical records.

The pattern of **warm nights** also exhibits significant variability, with a more pronounced upward trend than that recorded for warm days since 2000. The highest number of warm nights occurred in 2015 with 64 nights, while the lowest was recorded in 1976 with 2 nights, indicating a range of 62 days

between these values. The recent trend shows consistently elevated numbers of warm nights, with no fewer than 41 nights annually since 2014. In 2022, there were 74 warm nights, and in 2024, 70 nights were recorded, suggesting a continued increase in recent years.

Precipitation has generally been low with some fluctuations. The highest recorded was 668 mm in 1989 and the lowest was 100.9 mm in 2024, compared to an average range of 210–280 mm.

The number of **rainy days** has also varied, peaking at 43 days in 1989 and hitting a low of 14 in 1995,

Figure 4.13. Historical number of warm nights in the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: Adaptecca.

Figure 4.14. Rainfall history for the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: Adaptecca.

Figure 4.15. Historical number of rainy days in the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Source: Adaptecca.

with an average between 25 and 35 days per year. Despite lower overall rainfall, 2023 and 2024 saw high numbers of rainy days, reaching 47 and 41 respectively.

In summary, the climate of Huércal-Overa has shown a trend towards warming in recent decades, with the following characteristics:

- Average temperatures have increased, exceeding the historical range (17–18°C) and reaching 19.2°C in 2024.
- Thermal extremes have become more frequent, as both warm days and nights have risen steadily since 2000. For example, there were 114 warm

days in 2022, compared to a historical average of 35–45.

- Rainfall has generally decreased, with a new low recorded in 2024 at 100.9 mm. However, the number of rainy days remained relatively high in recent years (47 days in 2023), indicating that rain events may be more intense but shorter.

These developments are consistent with projections from organizations such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Future scenarios anticipate continued increases in temperature, more frequent warm days and nights, reduced precipitation, and an increased risk of desertification in the municipality.

USING CLIMAAX TOOLS FOR CLIMATE PREDICTION

5.1. Workflow 1: Heatwaves. EU-EuroHEAT health definition

5.1.1. Methodological description and process

The identification and analysis of heat waves in the municipality of Huércal-Overa were conducted in accordance with the EuroHEAT project methodology (Michelozzi et al., 2007). Within this framework, a heat wave is defined as any climatic event lasting at least two consecutive days during which both the maximum apparent temperature (Tappmax) and minimum apparent temperature (Tappmin) exceed the 90th percentile of the monthly climatology for the reference period 1971-2000.

For this study, daily meteorological data from the EURO-CORDEX grid (0.11° resolution, approximately 12 × 12 km) were utilized. The selected cell corresponds to coordinates 37.65°N and -2.02°W, representing Huércal-Overa. The analysis spans the period from 1986 to 2085 and considers two representative greenhouse gas concentration trajectories:

- RCP 4.5: A stabilization scenario with moderate mitigation measures.
- RCP 8.5: A high emissions scenario without significant reduction measures.

The approach comprises three main phases:

- **Data preprocessing:** Acquisition of daily temperature and relative humidity records from the EURO-CORDEX ESGF node, followed by spatial selection of the relevant cell and calculation of apparent temperature values.
- **Event identification and counting:** Application of the monthly 90th percentile thresholds (reference: 1971-2000) to Tappmax and Tappmin; days are classified as part of a heat wave only if included in events spanning at least two consecutive days.

- **Trend analysis:** Evaluation of long-term trends via second-degree polynomial fitting and linear regression for both RCP scenarios, assessing changes in the frequency, duration, and intensity of heat waves throughout the study period.

This methodology enables robust estimation of future heat wave evolution in Huércal-Overa and facilitates contextualization of their intensity and persistence relative to historical climate conditions—an essential component for effective risk assessment and adaptation planning.

5.1.2. Implementation of improvements

Several adaptations were made to enhance result comprehension and usability.

- **Integration of complementary data:** A second-degree polynomial trend analysis was added to smooth climate data variability, clarifying long-term patterns for easier understanding by non-experts.
- **Process automation:** Custom scripts automatically extract grid cell areas, implement EURO-CORDEX for Huércal-Overa, and generate refined CSV files ready for integration with other CLIMAX project tools, improving efficiency and reproducibility.

Standardized outputs now integrate directly with other modules, enabling links between climate data and socioeconomic or health indicators. This streamlines the identification of vulnerable groups to heat waves and supports targeted adaptation measures within LUGIA.

Figure 5.1. Heat wave days per year (RCP 4.5 vs. RCP 8.5, EU definition). Source: EuroHEAT (analysis with EURO-CORDEX ensemble). Prepared by the authors.

Figure 5.2. Heat wave days per year with quadratic fit (RCP 4.5 vs. RCP 8.5). Source: EuroHEAT / EURO-CORDEX. Prepared by the authors.

5.1.3. Results

The main analysis results are shown in graphic and table formats for easier understanding. We present annual heat wave days at lat 37.65°, lon -2.02° under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios. Annual bars use the EU health definition of heat waves, highlighting year-to-year variability and scenario differences. Quadratic fits display trends and acceleration across the century, with faster increases under RCP 8.5 and slower growth under RCP 4.5.

5.1.4. Conclusions

The graphs indicate a steady increase in annual heat wave days in Huércal-Overa. Under RCP 4.5, the rise is nearly linear; under RCP 8.5, growth is almost exponential (Figure 5.2). Currently, based on EU criteria, the municipality faces about 10 extreme heat days per year—over five more than in 2000 (Figure 5.1).

Projections show by 2060:

- **RCP 4.5:** Heat wave days may double to nearly 20 per year.
 - **RCP 8.5:** Days could triple to over 30 per year.
- In conclusion, climate change will significantly affect Huércal-Overa's environment and public health, emphasizing the need for immediate, locally tailored adaptation and mitigation measures.

5.2. Workflow 2: Heat waves. Local definition

5.2.1. Methodological description and process

This workflow centres on **heat wave assessment** using a definition tailored to the specific climatic and health circumstances of the municipality of Huércal-Overa. Here, a heat wave refers to any event where the **daily maximum temperature exceeds 35 °C for at least three consecutive days**. This threshold was chosen due to its **relevance for public health**, as it correlates with increased medical risks for the local community and recent observed impacts.

For analysis, climate data from the **EURO-CORDEX** project were employed, integrating the global climate model MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR with the regional climate model **CLMcom-CLM-CCLM4-8-17**. The dataset, featuring an approximate spatial resolution of **12 km**, spans the period from **1971 to 2100**. This range enables the inclusion of both historical records and future climate projections under emissions scenarios RCP 4.5 (moderate mitigation) and RCP 8.5 (high emissions). Due to gaps in certain years, some intervals could not be represented in the time series or visualised in the graphs.

The **methodological procedure** applied in this analysis consists of the following stages:

- **Data acquisition and initial preparation:** Daily maximum and minimum temperature **records (at 2 metres above ground)** were collected for both historical (1971–2005) and future (2006–2100) periods via the CDS Copernicus service using its API. Post-download, data underwent decompression, cleaning, and organised storage for efficient processing.

- **Study region selection and spatial cropping:** An interactive map interface (**Leaflet**) was used to delineate a region centred on Huércal-Overa. Selected coordinates in the **WGS84** system were then transformed to the EURO-CORDEX (Rotated Pole) reference system to ensure data compatibility.

- **Calculation of heat wave indices using Xclim:** Using processed data, heat wave indicators specific to the local context (maximum temperature > 35 °C for ≥ 3 consecutive days) were computed with the **Xclim** library. Key indicators generated included:

- Heat Wave Index (HWI): Total annual days within heat waves
- Heat Wave Frequency (HWF): Number of distinct heat wave events per year
- Heat Wave Total Length (HWTL): Aggregate number of heat wave days per year
- **Average Event Duration:** Mean duration of individual heat wave events annually

- **Result storage and reprojection:** Indicator values were saved as raster **GeoTIFF** files and reprojected into the **WGS84** geographic system to enhance interoperability with other GIS tools.

- **Extraction and visualisation of local time series:** Localised time series were generated for the precise point of Huércal-Overa, followed by the development of interactive visualisations using **Matplotlib** and **Plotly**. These visual outputs facilitate analysis of annual indicator trends across different climate scenarios (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5).

In conclusion, this workflow provides a comprehensive methodological framework adapted to Huércal-Overa's local context for heat wave evaluation. By leveraging high-resolution data, specialised indices, and interactive graphical outputs, the approach enables detailed characterisation of both historical and projected developments of heat waves, offering a reliable technical foundation for directing climate adaptation strategies and public health protection measures.

5.2.2. Implementation of improvements

To improve the usefulness, accuracy, and clarity of results, several key methodological updates were made:

- The Rothfus index (actual thermal sensation), which factors in both temperature and humidity, was incorporated to better estimate how heat is perceived by the population. This is especially important for assessing public health risks in humid conditions.
- The code now supports flexible parameterization with YAML files, enabling easy adjustments and sensitivity tests for various scenarios.
- Automated scripts generate standardized outputs, including interactive graphics and organized CSV files, ensuring interoperability with other project modules and effective communication with non-technical stakeholders.

These enhancements make the workflow more robust, adaptable, and practical, supporting more reliable climate planning and decision-making in Huércal-Overa.

5.2.3. Results

This section presents the results obtained for the annual extreme heat indicators at the study site (latitude 37.65°, longitude -2.02°), calculated using the selected GCM-RCM combination. For each

indicator, two complementary types of graphical representations were generated:

- **Time series with linear fit** facilitate a direct comparison of trend evolution under the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios, enabling identification of notable differences in both the magnitude and rate of change between a moderate mitigation scenario and a high emissions scenario.
- **Bar charts broken down by year** are valuable for assessing interannual variability and identifying singular events within both historical and projected data, such as years exhibiting significant increases in extreme heat or intervals of relative stabilization that contextualize long-term trends.

The **analyzed indicators** include:

- Rothfus Heat Index (HI)
- Total number of days in heat wave
- Average annual duration per heat wave event
- Annual frequency of heat waves
- Heat-Wave Index (number of days classified as part of heat waves)

Heat waves were identified by applying the following threshold: three or more consecutive days with maximum temperatures exceeding 35°C and minimum temperatures above 0°C. This criterion effectively captures extended periods of intense heat that are particularly relevant for impact assessments in the municipality.

Rothfusz Heat Index (HI) - (Degrees Celsius)

Figura 5.3. Rothfusz Heat Index: annual trend (RCP 4.5 vs. RCP 8.5). Annual dispersion and linear fit lines. Source: GCM-RCM output (mpi_m_mpi_esm_lr - clmcom_clm_cclm4_8_17). Prepared by the authors.

Figura 5.4. Rothfusz Heat Index: annual bars (RCP 4.5 vs. RCP 8.5). Source: GCM-RCM indicated. Prepared by the authors.

Total number of days in heat wave

Figure 5.5. Total days in heat waves: annual trend (RCP 4.5 vs. RCP 8.5). Annual dispersion and linear fit lines. Source: GCM–RCM indicated. Prepared by the authors.

Figure 5.6. Total days in heat wave: annual bars (RCP 4.5 vs. RCP 8.5). Source: GCM–RCM indicated. Prepared by the authors.

Average duration per event

Figure 5.7. Average event duration: annual trend (RCP 4.5 vs. RCP 8.5). Annual dispersion and linear fit lines. Source: GCM-RCM indicated. Prepared by the authors.

Figure 5.8. Average heat wave duration: annual bars (RCP 4.5 vs. RCP 8.5). Source: GCM-RCM indicated. Prepared by the authors.

Annual frequency of heat waves

Figure 5.9. Annual heat wave frequency: trend (RCP 4.5 vs. RCP 8.5). Annual dispersion and linear fit lines. Source: GCM-RCM indicated. Prepared by the authors.

Figure 5.10. Heat wave frequency: annual bars (RCP 4.5 vs. RCP 8.5). Source: GCM-RCM indicated. Prepared by the authors.

Heat-Wave Index

Figure 5.11. Heat-Wave Index: annual trend (RCP 4.5 vs. RCP 8.5). Annual dispersion and linear fit lines. Source: GCM–RCM indicated. Prepared by the authors.

Figure 5.12. Heat-Wave Index: annual bars (RCP 4.5 vs. RCP 8.5). Source: GCM–RCM indicated. Prepared by the authors.

5.2.4. Conclusions

The main conclusions derived from the analysis of the selected climate indicators for the municipality of Huércal-Overa are presented below:

Rothfusz Heat Index (HI)

This indicator combines air temperature and relative humidity to estimate the thermal sensation perceived by the human body. It is expressed in degrees Celsius (°C) or Fahrenheit (°F), but does not represent an actual temperature; rather, it estimates physiological heat stress experienced by individuals. Values below 27°C are associated with thermal comfort and minimal health risks. Temperatures above this threshold indicate increasingly muggy conditions, and levels over 32°C correspond to heat stress, which intensifies as values rise.

The municipality of Huércal-Overa records average annual historical values above 27°C, with projections suggesting temperatures may approach 28°C under RCP 4.5 and exceed 29°C under RCP 8.5 by 2060 (Figure 5.3). As a result, there is a potential for persistent sensations of discomfort and fatigue due to prolonged exposure. However, values of 32°C, the threshold for classifying heat stress, are not expected to be reached in any scenario considered, including extreme years (Figure 5.4).

Total number of days in Heat Wave

Projections indicate an upward trend: from a historical average of 10 days, the count could exceed 15 days by 2060 under RCP 4.5 and surpass 20 days under RCP 8.5. These represent increases of 50% and 100%, respectively (Figure 5.5). In the most severe forecast years, over 30 or 40 heat wave days could occur annually (Figure 5.6), equating to more than one month per summer under heightened conditions.

Average duration per event

Currently, the average duration of a heatwave is less than 3 days, but projections show this could double to nearly 6 days in both scenarios by 2060 (Figure 5.7). In extreme years, episodes may last over 8 days (Figure 5.8), indicating increased risk due to extended exposure.

Annual frequency of Heat Waves

The frequency of heat waves is projected to rise from approximately two per year historically, to about four annually by 2060 in both scenarios (Figure 5.9), representing a 100% increase. During peak years, more than six or seven episodes may occur each year (Figure 5.10), suggesting a shift toward frequent summer heat stress.

Heat-Wave Index

This index quantifies the cumulative annual number of heat wave days, reflecting overall population and environmental exposure to risk. Higher values indicate greater cumulative exposure. Values under 5 days/year denote low occurrence; between 5–15 days/year, extreme heat becomes recurrent; and more than 20–30 days/year represent prolonged extreme heat with significant impacts.

Currently, the municipality exceeds the 5 days/year threshold (Figure 5.11), indicating that health risks, particularly for vulnerable groups, are a present concern. Projections show that under RCP 8.5, the 20-day threshold could be consistently met by 2040 (Figure 5.12), with implications for public health, urban systems, energy use, and economic productivity. Occasional exceedance of 30 days/year is also possible before this time (Figure 5.12).

In summary, projections indicate that the municipality of Huércal-Overa is likely to experience an ongoing intensification of heat waves in terms of frequency, duration, and severity. This will have direct effects on public health and urban living conditions. While the Rothfusz index may not reach critical levels for heat stress, the increasing trend in perceived heat stress, coupled with a growing number and duration of heat wave events, suggests summers will become periods of heightened climate risk.

The Heat-Wave Index supports this assessment, showing that under the RCP 8.5 scenario, Huércal-Overa may face sustained extreme heat in coming decades with notable effects on public health, ecosystems, energy consumption, and the local economy. These findings highlight the importance of prioritizing urban adaptation strategies, especially those involving nature-based solutions, to support adaptation and mitigation efforts.

APPLICATION OF CLIMAAX TOOLS FOR RISK PREDICTION

6.1. Workflow 3: Risk assessment with historical satellite data.

6.1.1. Methodological description and process

This workflow evaluates the spatial risk of extreme heat exposure in Huércal-Overa using historical satellite data from summer 2016, the hottest year in the dataset. The methodology addresses two main aspects of climate risk: exposure and vulnerability.

- Exposure (Surface Temperature, LST):** surface temperature data (LST) was sourced from Landsat-8 at 30 m resolution, using six cloud-free images from June to the end of summer. A raster mosaic showing maximum surface temperatures per pixel was created and classified into ten health risk categories, ranging from “Very low” (<20–25 °C) to “Very high” (55–60 °C).
- Vulnerability (Population Distribution):** Population data from WorldPop (100 m resolution) and census data from INE (2021) were used to identify groups most vulnerable to extreme heat—specifically children aged 0–4 and adults over 65. This enabled the creation of a **detailed vulnerability map** with categories from “Very low” to “Very high”.
- Satellite data collection and preprocessing:** This phase involved automated downloading and decompression of Landsat-8 images, selection of scenes with low cloud cover, and the creation of a raster mosaic representing the maximum surface temperature recorded during the summer of 2016.
- Heat exposure classification:** Continuous surface temperature values were reclassified into discrete categories in order to facilitate interpretation related to health risk and environmental exposure.
- Combined spatial analysis:** Satellite and population data were reprojected to a common

Exposure and vulnerability components were combined using a **risk matrix** to produce a **geo-referenced climate risk estimate**. This approach supports both risk quantification and mapping to identify municipal hotspots. The analysis was performed at two scales—the full municipality and the urban area—to better reflect daily realities and to prioritize adaptation measures that improve residents' quality of life.

The analysis was divided into several structured phases:

Figure 6.1. Landsat-8 series (summer 2016): Average LST by date. Source: Landsat-8 OLI/TIRS (2016). Prepared by the authors.

Figure 6.2. 10x10 risk matrix. Source: Prepared by the authors based on the study methodology.

Figure 6.3. Units of analysis. Source: INE (Census districts). Prepared by the authors.

reference system (Lambert Azimuthal Equal-Area, EPSG:3035) to ensure consistent geospatial analyses. This step resulted in maps for the urban and municipal area of Huércal-Overa, illustrating the spatial intersection of heat exposure and population vulnerability.

- **Generation of quantitative metrics and visualization:** Metrics related to each exposure and vulnerability category were calculated and represented using pie charts, interactive graphs, and dynamic maps. Scatter plots of average surface temperatures on selected dates were also included to support identification of critical episodes.
- **Final risk assessment:** Exposure and vulnerability information were integrated via a risk matrix (exposure x vulnerability), producing a final population climate risk map. This map identified areas within the municipality relevant for planning adaptation policies and managing risks associated with heat waves.

6.1.2. Implementation of improvements

To enhance the quality and relevance of the analysis, several modifications were made compared to the initial approach:

- **Correction and population adjustment:** Updated census data from INE (2021) was incorporated to supplement WorldPop, the primary source used in the CLIMAAX methodology. This integration addressed the common underestimation of populations by WorldPop in densely populated urban areas; this model allocates population based on spatial averages and general density criteria, which may not reflect actual concentrations in compact residential zones. This adjustment supports more accurate integration of economic and sociodemographic data in later phases, improving population vulnerability estimates through the development of a multivariate vulnerability index.
- **Advanced workflow automation:** Extraction, filtering, classification, and spatial analysis steps were automated using specific Python scripts, to ensure reproducibility, efficient data processing, and scalability for analyses across different periods or regions.

- **New analytical tools and advanced visualization:** Custom functions enabled automatic generation of comparative charts, including pie charts and area graphs, illustrating the proportion of surface area exposed to each risk level. Interactive comparative maps were also introduced for simultaneous examination of thermal exposure and population vulnerability distribution.
- **Production of interoperable results:** Final outputs were exported in standard formats (GeoTIFF for raster data and GeoPackage for vector data), facilitating integration with external GIS systems and enabling direct use by local administrations for territorial planning and preparing responses to extreme heat events.

6.1.3. Results

This section outlines the findings from the combined analysis of population and thermal exposure data. Demographic information was sourced from census records (INE, 2021) and supplemented with global data provided by WorldPop (2025). Thermal exposure estimates were derived from Landsat-8 satellite data for summer 2016, selected due to elevated temperatures and minimal cloud coverage, conditions suitable for satellite observations. The integration of these datasets enabled the mapping of vulnerable population distribution in relation to areas experiencing significant overheating, resulting in a detailed representation of climate risk.

The following figures illustrate several variables examined in the analysis:

- Structure of total and vulnerable populations.
- Spatial distribution of thermal exposure.
- Overlay of both factors on risk maps.

Analysis using WorldPop data (CLIMAAX Methodology)

Structure of the total and vulnerable population

Analysis with information from Worldpop

Figure 6.4. Vulnerable population density (WorldPop 2025): urban and municipal. Source: WorldPop 2025 (density). Prepared by the authors.

Figure 6.5. Proportion of surface area by vulnerable population density category (municipality vs. urban area). Source: WorldPop 2025. Prepared by the authors.

Analysis with information from the INE

Figure 6.6. Total population in urban and municipal areas. Source: INE (2021/2024). Prepared by the authors.

Figure 6.7. Total vulnerable population aged 0–4 and ≥65 (municipality and urban area). Source: INE (2024). © OpenStreetMap contributors. Prepared by the authors.

Figure 6.8. Proportion of vulnerable population (urban and municipal). Source: INE (2024). Prepared by the authors.

Figure 6.9. Total area by vulnerable population density category (INE). Source: INE (2021/2024). Prepared by the authors.

Analysis with information from Worldpop + INE

Population-density comparison (Census vs. WorldPop)

Figure 6.10. Vulnerable population density: comparison of sources. Source: WorldPop 2025; INE (2024). Prepared by the authors.

Share of vulnerable population (INE)

Figure 6.11. Proportion of vulnerable population (0–4 and ≥65 years). Source: WorldPop 2025 + adjustment with INE. Prepared by the authors.

Spatial distribution of thermal exposure

Figure 6.12. Overheated zones (exposure) in urban and municipal areas. Source: Landsat-8 OLI/TIRS (2016). Prepared by the authors.

Figure 6.13. Surface area distribution by overheating category (LST 2016). Source: Landsat-8 OLI/TIRS (2016). Prepared by the authors.

Overlay of both factors on risk maps

Analysis with information from Worldpop

Figure 6.14. Municipal level: Exposure (LST) and vulnerability (density of vulnerable population) — Municipal level. Source: Landsat-8 OLI/TIRS (2016); WorldPop 2025. Prepared by the authors.

Figure 6.15. Urban setting: Exposure (LST) and vulnerability (density of vulnerable population) — Municipal level. Source: Landsat-8 OLI/TIRS (2016); WorldPop 2025. Prepared by the authors.

Heat-exposure vs Population-vulnerability Risk map

Derived from WorldPop 2025 density data

Figure 6.16. Risk map: Result of the risk matrix (exposure × vulnerability) grouped into five levels. Source: Landsat-8 OLI/TIRS (2016); WorldPop 2025. Prepared by the authors.

Analysis with information from the INE

Risk Map: Municipality vs. Locality

Figure 6.17. Risk map: Result of the risk matrix (exposure × vulnerability) grouped into five levels. Source: Landsat-8 (2016); INE (2024); reference orthoimage. Prepared by the authors.

Possible heat risk level to vulnerable population

Figure 6.18. Climate risk map in relation to reference green elements and urban residential spaces (blue masses). Source: Landsat-8 (2016); INE (2024); OSM base cartography. Prepared by the authors.

6.1.4. Conclusions

To assess climate risk in the municipality of Huércal-Overa, this analysis considers thermal exposure and climate vulnerability variables:

Vulnerable population

This study identifies groups at greater risk from extreme heat based on age (adults over 65 and children under 4). These groups were identified using demographic data from INE and Worldpop.

Worldpop data indicate that the town of Huércal-Overa has the highest concentration of vulnerable population within the municipality (Figure 6.4), mainly situated in its urban center. This central area covers only 1.4% of the municipal territory (Figure 6.5) but contains a large proportion of this population group. Within this zone, higher densities (9.3%) are observed around Adolfo Suárez Municipal Park and the health center. By contrast, the density of vulnerable populations decreases in other areas of the town, especially towards the northern and southern limits. This distribution reflects the demographic significance of Huércal-Overa relative to other settlements in the municipality.

Data from INE point to higher overall population numbers in western and northern parts of the municipality, as well as in the town of Huércal-Overa (Figure 6.7), with a higher proportion of vulnerable individuals in the northern sector, followed by certain areas within Huércal-Overa (Figure 6.8). Consequently, 71.2% of the municipality and 21.9% of the urban area of Huércal-Overa include vulnerable populations (Figure 6.9).

Within Huércal-Overa, the population is largely concentrated in the northern, southern, and central-western regions (Figure 6.7), aligning with areas of higher density of vulnerable groups. These concentrations appear primarily on the northern and southern boundaries and the central-western section near the health center (Figure 6.8).

Combining both demographic sources highlights the northern part of the municipality and the town of Huércal-Overa as areas with the greatest population vulnerability. In the town, particularly high densities are found in the central-eastern area near Adolfo Suárez Municipal Park and the

central-southern region near the Huércal-Overa employment office (Figure 6.11).

Thermal exposure

This indicator tracks soil surface temperature (LST) to pinpoint areas with the highest heat exposure. The central and northern parts of the municipality, particularly Huércal-Overa, experience elevated thermal exposure, while southern and eastern zones are cooler due to more vegetation and proximity to the Almanzora River.

Within Huércal-Overa, the northern area—including the Molineta neighborhood and Hospital de la Inmaculada—has the highest thermal exposure, with an additional hotspot near Príncipe Felipe Primary School in the south. Overall, 12.8% of the municipal area faces very high heat risk, but Huércal-Overa itself is entirely within this high-risk zone.

Climate risk

Combining population vulnerability and thermal exposure shows that climate risk is highest in central and northern Huércal-Overa, where vulnerable populations also concentrate. Urban analysis confirms higher temperatures in the north, but the most at-risk populations are in the center-south. Risk mapping consistently highlights the north and center as top concern areas, with medium risk in the south and center-east.

Including green and residential spaces refines the risk map, revealing limited vegetation in several key high-risk zones, especially around Villa de Huércal-Overa Theater and the employment office. These areas should be targeted for mitigation efforts.

In summary, Huércal-Overa's urban core is most at risk from heat waves, particularly its northern and southern sections with dense vulnerable populations and insufficient vegetation. Targeted adaptation measures are urgently needed here.

6.2. Workflow 4: Risk assessment with climate projections

6.2.1. Methodological description and process

This workflow presents a spatial assessment of future climate risk linked to the expected increase in heat waves affecting vulnerable populations within the municipality of Huércal-Overa. The methodology employs high-resolution climate projections generated under the Copernicus programme and is guided by EuroHEAT project protocols, which are widely adopted for evaluating health impacts associated with extreme heat across Europe.

The assessment considers two Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) as defined by the IPCC:

- **RCP 4.5:** An intermediate scenario involving partial mitigation measures that moderately restrict emissions growth.
- **RCP 8.5:** A high-emission scenario without mitigation actions.

Two temporal horizons are evaluated to capture the progression of climate risk:

- Near Future (2016–2045)
- Distant Future (2046–2075)

Heat waves are defined according to the European Health Thresholds established by EuroHEAT: periods of at least two consecutive days during which both maximum and minimum daily apparent temperatures surpass the 90th percentile relative to the reference climatology (1986–2015). This definition supports consistent identification of health-relevant risk conditions within the European context.

The methodological framework consists of several distinct phases to enhance result robustness and reproducibility:

- **Data Acquisition and Preparation:** Temperature data measured at 2 meters above ground were automatically retrieved from the Climate Data Store (Copernicus), including both historical records and future projections (1986–2075). These time series were pre-processed—

extracting maximum and minimum apparent temperatures—and spatially cropped to focus solely on Huércal-Overa.

- **Calculation of Projected Variation in Heat Wave Days:** Historical averages for the baseline period (1986–2015) were compared to future periods (2016–2045 and 2046–2075). Relative percentage changes were estimated, facilitating the creation of raster maps that illustrate the spatial magnitude of projected increases in heat wave frequency.
- **Zonal Statistics of Relative Change:** The resultant change maps were reprojected and overlaid with the municipality’s census tracts using spatial analysis techniques. Zonal statistics were then derived to reflect average projected changes within each census unit, generating vector layers enriched with these data.
- **Classification of Projected Relative Change:** Results were organized into ten equidistant intervals, enabling clear and uniform thematic mapping. These categories, ranging from *Very Low* to *Very High*, support interpretation by both local stakeholders and non-specialist audiences.
- **Integration of Demographic Data for Vulnerability Assessment:** Two primary demographic datasets were used. First, WorldPop supplies high-resolution (100 m) population data integral to the CLIMAAX methodology. Second, official data from INE (2024) offer enhanced precision, particularly in urban settings. Both datasets were reclassified into equidistant intervals to generate age-based vulnerability maps.
- **Combining Exposure and Vulnerability to Determine Risk:** Exposure (relative changes in heat wave days) and vulnerability (density of at-risk populations) were quantitatively combined using a risk matrix, producing final maps that classify areas into five risk levels: Very Low, Low, Medium, High, and Very High.

These results deliver detailed insights into the projected evolution of climate risk in Huércal-Overa under both RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios for the near (2016–2045) and distant (2046–2075) future timeframes.

Figure 6.19. 10x10 risk matrix (future exposure × vulnerability). Source: Prepared by the authors.

6.2.2. Implementation of improvements

To enhance the robustness, clarity, and practical relevance of the outcomes, several key refinements were introduced to the original methodological framework. These enhancements not only improved the analytical rigor but also strengthened the utility of the results for urban planning and climate adaptation decision-making:

- Process Automation:** The workflow was fully automated using Python scripts, encompassing direct API downloads, data reprojection, spatial analysis, automatic map generation, and shapefile management. This automation enabled greater efficiency, ensured reproducibility, and facilitated the replication of analyses across varying temporal horizons or geographic regions.
- Enriched and Comparative Visualization:** Comparative visualizations were deployed using a parallel (2x2) layout that displayed results from distinct timeframes and climate scenarios concurrently. This approach allowed for clear, direct comparison between scenarios, supporting both scientific interpretation and
- Integration of Census Data:** The inclusion of official population statistics from INE notably enhanced analytical accuracy by cross-referencing and augmenting satellite-derived data from WorldPop. This integration yielded a more reliable depiction of vulnerable populations at the local scale, reinforcing the demographic dimension of risk assessment.
- Detailed and Clear Cartography:** Symbolization and legends within the cartographic outputs were optimized to ensure more effective visual communication. Risk categories were intuitively presented, enabling immediate comprehension by municipal managers and officials.
- Sectional-Level Spatialization:** Analyses were conducted at the census tract level, achieving a spatial resolution critical for local planning efforts. This methodology allows for targeted identification of municipal areas facing the greatest future heatwave risks, thereby supporting prioritization of adaptation measures as

effective communication with non-specialist stakeholders.

well as informed territorial management of infrastructure and public services.

These methodological improvements have resulted in an analysis distinguished by enhanced technical depth and spatial precision, positioning it as a strategic tool for projecting future climate risk scenarios. By enabling straightforward comparisons across time horizons, emission scenarios, and spatial population units, the findings offer a robust and actionable foundation on which to base urban planning and adaptation policies in Huércal-Overa.

6.2.3. Results

This section compiles the visual outputs of the analysis and structures them into three main

blocks, systematically comparing municipal and urban areas in relation to climate projections. It contrasts findings from the historical reference period (1986–2015) with projections for the future horizon (2046–2075). The analysis uses three data sets:

- Population and vulnerability,
- Thermal exposure (LST),
- Risk synthesis (exposure × vulnerability).

The figures provide information to identify hotspots where high temperatures coincide with higher concentrations of vulnerable populations, quantify the proportion of territory in each risk category, and determine priorities for intervention at both the municipal scale and within the consolidated urban fabric.

Thermal exposure (projected increase in annual heat wave days)

Analysis with information from Worldpop

Figure 6.20. Relative change in the annual number of heat wave days (%). Source: Climate projections (RCP 4.5/8.5). Prepared by the authors.

Figure 6.21. Reclassified magnitude of change (1–10). Source: Climate projections (RCP 4.5/8.5). Prepared by the authors.

Risk synthesis (exposure × vulnerability)

Figure 6.22. Future risk (municipality) using WorldPop vulnerability. Source: Climate projections (RCP 4.5/8.5); WorldPop 2025. Prepared by the authors.

Figure 6.23. Future risk (urban area) using WorldPop vulnerability. Source: Climate projections (RCP 4.5/8.5); WorldPop 2025. Prepared by the authors.

Risk synthesis (exposure × vulnerability)

Analysis with information from the INE

Figure 6.24. Future risk (municipality) using INE vulnerability. Source: Climate projections (RCP 4.5/8.5); INE (2024). Prepared by the authors.

Figure 6.25. Future risk (urban area) using INE vulnerability. Source: Climate projections (RCP 4.5/8.5); INE (2024). Prepared by the authors.

6.2.4. Conclusions

The following presents the findings of an evaluation of climate and demographic projections concerning future risk in the municipality of Huércal-Overa, with emphasis on the impact of heat waves. The analysis incorporates IPCC emissions scenarios (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5) across near- and long-term timeframes, integrating climate, thermal, and demographic data from WorldPop and INE. The aim is to determine patterns of thermal exposure over time and the population groups most likely to be affected.

Analysis of Projected Changes in Annual Heat Wave Days

IPCC projections indicate increases in temperature and frequency of heat waves. Two climate scenarios were analyzed based on anticipated anthropogenic emissions:

- **RCP Scenario 4.5 (moderate mitigation):** For 2016-2045, a 150% increase in relative heat wave days is projected; for 2046-2075, increases may reach approximately 300% in the most sensitive areas. Southern and eastern parts of the municipality, currently cooler zones, are expected to experience proportionally larger increases in heat waves (Figure 6.20). Risk classification shows levels 4 and 5 for these critical areas in the respective periods (Figure 6.21).
- **RCP Scenario 8.5 (high emissions):** More substantial changes are projected: around a 200% increase in hot days for 2016-2045, and over 600% by 2046-2075 in much of the region. These changes would predominantly affect the southern and eastern areas, increasing their thermal vulnerability (Figure 6.20). Correspondingly, risk levels could rise from level 4 to level 10 (Figure 6.21).

Risk Summary: Assessment of Thermal Exposure in Vulnerable Population Groups

WorldPop data suggests that population vulnerability will remain concentrated in Huércal-Overa under both scenarios. Projections indicate medium-high risk for RCP 4.5 and higher risk for RCP 8.5. The southeastern municipality is also expected to reach moderate-high risk under more adverse scenarios (Figure 6.22). Within Huércal-Overa,

the area between Adolfo Suárez Municipal Park and the employment office is identified as having the highest risk, particularly the central-eastern zone. Under RCP 4.5 for 2046-2075, this location is classified as high risk, which rises to very high risk under RCP 8.5. During this later period, high risk is widespread throughout the southern and central municipality, while only the northern section maintains a moderate level (Figure 6.23).

INE data produces similar results to those obtained from WorldPop. The greatest climatic risk is centered in the town of Huércal-Overa, followed by the southeastern portion of the municipality. Risk projections are moderate for RCP 4.5 and high for RCP 8.5 (Figure 6.24).

Within urban zones, some differences emerge between WorldPop and INE analyses. The risk is more specific to the central-eastern area around the employment office according to INE, while other central and southern sectors show lower risk levels: low-medium for RCP 4.5 and moderate-high for RCP 8.5 in 2016-2045. The central-southern area is reported as high risk for RCP 4.5 and very high for RCP 8.5 within that period (Figure 6.25).

These observations complement previous analyses indicating that the central and southern areas of Huércal-Overa are priority areas for action.

In summary, projections suggest that the urban core of Huércal-Overa—especially central and southern regions—will encounter elevated climate risk linked to heat waves in the coming decades. Alignment between scenarios and data sources supports the assessment's validity and assists in spatial prioritization for interventions, particularly along the axis between the employment office, Guillermo Reyna area, and Levante Polyclinic. This provides a strategic framework for urban planning, focusing on nature-based solutions and adaptation measures where thermal exposure and population vulnerability coincide.

STAKEHOLDERS

An initial identification of the project's stakeholders is being carried out, integrating various sectors and groups in the municipality that could be affected by the impacts of climate change, particularly the increase in heat waves.

Likewise, those stakeholders who, due to their experience, roles, or institutional responsibilities, can influence the design, implementation, and social acceptance of the proposed nature-based solutions are included.

This preliminary identification will serve as a basis for structuring future participation, collaboration, and communication actions, ensuring an inclusive approach adapted to the local context. Institutional stakeholders, as well as representatives from the social fabric and from the technical and business sectors, are included.

Below is a list of identified entities, including a justification and prioritization of their relevance to the project.

Table 7.1. Stakeholder identification and characterization matrix.

Name	Justification	Priority
TYPE: INSTITUTIONAL SECTOR		
Huércal-Overa Public Services Management, S.L.U.	A municipal company responsible for urban services such as green area maintenance, cleaning, and water supply, key to the implementation and maintenance of nature-based solutions for urban cooling.	1
Civil defense	An essential service for rapid response to climate emergencies, coordinating volunteers and resources to respond quickly during heat waves, including the transportation of vulnerable people.	1
Huércal-Overa Regional Agricultural Office	A key entity in planning and consulting for the agricultural sector, relevant to water management. In Huércal-Overa advises farmers and ranchers, being able to influence practices that reduce the impact of heat on rural and peri-urban areas.	2
TYPE: HEALTH SECTOR AND RELATED ASSOCIATIONS		
Huércal-Overa Health Center	Primary health care is key to detecting and treating cases resulting from heat waves, especially in vulnerable populations.	1
La Inmaculada Hospital	Regional hospital that handles emergencies and hospitalizations for heat stroke and other conditions aggravated by extreme heat. This is important for implementing heat wave protocols.	1

Table 7.1. Stakeholder identification and characterization matrix.

Name	Justification	Priority
TYPE: SECTOR SALUD Y ASOCIACIONES RELACIONADAS		
Spanish Association Against Cancer	It serves people with cancer, a highly vulnerable population due to treatments and weakened immune systems who may require specific thermal protection measures.	1
Association of People with Disabilities "Virgen del Río"	It offers daily support and services to people with varying degrees of dependency, who may have a reduced ability to adapt to extreme heat events.	1
Alzheimer's Association	It serves people with cognitive impairment who are highly vulnerable due to difficulty recognizing and responding to extreme heat.	1
Association of Women Affected by Fibromyalgia	It brings together women with chronic conditions that can be aggravated by extreme temperatures.	2
Virgen del Río Occupational Center	Center serving people with intellectual disabilities who are at high risk of heat waves and who may require adapted prevention plans during episodes of extreme heat.	1
ASTEVA Huércal-Overa, Association of families of people with ASD and PDD.	It brings together families and individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder who may have altered thermal perception and difficulty reacting to extreme heat.	1
FAISEM Huércal-Overa, Andalusian Association for the Integration of the Mentally Ill.	It serves people with serious mental illnesses, including those on drug treatment that increases their vulnerability to extreme heat.	1
TYPE: NEIGHBORHOOD ASSOCIATIONS		
Asociación de Úrcal Úrcal Association "The Labors of Atocha." The Labors. "La Hoya Waterwheel." La Hoya. "Almajal". Almajalejo. "Virgin of the Snows." Saint Mary of Nieva. "La Morena-Venta Civil" "The Garden." Rambla Grande. "The Puertecico" "The Immaculate Conception and Christ the King." La Concepción, Overa. "The Old Jumper" "La Fuensanta-Erre" San Francisco	Neighborhood associations can play a key role as a channel for communication and community mobilization in the implementation of adaptation and prevention measures against extreme heat. Furthermore, their participation is essential for incorporating neighborhood perceptions and needs into the design of Nature-Based Solutions that will transform their immediate surroundings.	2

Table 7.1. Stakeholder identification and characterization matrix.

Name	Justification	Priority
TYPE: SECTOR SALUD Y ASOCIACIONES RELACIONADAS		
"The Age of the Virgin"		
"The Vineyards"		
"Montecastillo"		
"The Fourteen Seasons"		
"The Pine Ferris Wheel"		
"Historic center"		
"The Watchtower"		
"The Fauna"		
"The Stove"		
TYPE: SENIOR ASSOCIATIONS AND CENTERS		
"Ángeles Parra" Senior Residence Little Sisters of Helpless Elderly People	People over 65 are especially vulnerable to heat waves, a vulnerability often exacerbated by dependency and chronic illness. This combination significantly increases their sensitivity to high temperatures, making these centers a priority for implementing solutions that help mitigate the effects of extreme heat.	1
"La Moncloa". Overa.		
"The Rivera of Santa María de Nieva"		
"The Jasmines 2001". San Francisco.		
"Sierra Enmedio". The Norias.		
"Virgin of Sorrows." Úrcal.		
"The Pines." San Isidro.		
"The Cradle of Bolillo"		
Active participation center for seniors.		
Caritas Huércal-Overa Without Borders Association "Ukraine in the Heart" Senegalese Immigrant Association of Huércal-Overa. Moroccan Association Achrouk (Dawn). In progress. Huércal-Overa Integra Association Lithuanian Community Association of the Levante de Almería	People at risk of social exclusion, with limited resources, or of migrant origin often live in living conditions that increase their vulnerability to heat waves. Therefore, it is essential to have associations that bring together these groups, both to ensure effective communication of actions and to facilitate the implementation of improvement measures. These organizations also act as a direct link with specific migrant communities, facilitating the dissemination of information and the early detection of needs during extreme heat waves.	1
TYPE: EDUCATION SECTOR		
I. E. S. Albujaia	Schools serve populations considered highly vulnerable, especially those at young ages.	2
I. E. S. Cura Valera		
C. E. I. P. Príncipe Felipe	Furthermore, these are places where renaturalization measures to combat heat waves would be a priority, so it would be essential to understand the perceptions of their users. They can become places where heat-mitigation measures are disseminated.	
C. E. I. P. Virgen del Río		
C. E. I. P. San José de Calasanz		
C. P. R. Stays		

Table 7.1. Stakeholder identification and characterization matrix.

Name	Justification	Priority
TYPE: ECONOMIC SECTOR		
Irrigation Community of the Northern Zone of Huércal-Overa El Saltador Irrigation Community G´ s España ADSG Huércal-Overa and Levante Almeriense Gabarrón Rodríguez Agricultural Company, S. L. Agrolevante SAT Agricultural Commercial BPZ, S. L. Industrial Agrícola Belzunces, S. L. HOS Association “Cluster for the Sustainable Development of the Pork Sector”	The agricultural and livestock sector plays a significant role in the efficient management of water and vegetation, as well as in the adoption of practices that promote climate adaptation in productive environments. Agriculture, through the proper management of crops, hedges, trees, and ground cover, can also contribute to mitigating extreme heat and improving the local microclimate, thus reinforcing the benefits of nature-based solutions.	2

In later phases, all relevant associations, institutions, and groups will be consulted to inform the development and refinement of nature-based solutions. Their input will also help identify vulnerable populations and areas at highest risk from extreme heat. This collaborative approach ensures adaptation measures are practical, accepted, and meet the needs of Huércal-Overa residents.

GENERAL CONCLUSIONS FOR HUÉRCAL OVERA

The initial analysis confirms that Huércal-Overa is highly exposed and vulnerable to extreme heat, posing an immediate climate challenge. This vulnerability stems from its semi-arid Mediterranean climate, hot summers, reliance on agriculture and services, limited green spaces, and sparse vegetation, all of which hamper thermal regulation.

Climate models predict a significant increase in heatwave frequency, duration, and intensity throughout the century, especially in high-emission scenarios (RCP 8.5), making extreme heat events more common and threatening public health, the economy, and urban ecosystems.

Spatial risk assessments indicate that the highest climate risks are concentrated in the urban center, particularly among vulnerable groups like the elderly and young children, with priority intervention areas identified in the north, south, and central zones near major parks and avenues.

By integrating local and global data sources, the study pinpoints critical areas—mainly in the city center and south—where low vegetation and population density heighten vulnerability. These insights underscore the need for nature-based solutions such as expanding urban green spaces to lower temperatures and protect residents.

This phase offers a strong scientific foundation for adaptation planning, highlighting both general trends and specific high-risk areas. The robust methodology supports targeted mitigation and adaptation measures.

Huércal-Overa must now translate this understanding into action through a coordinated strategy involving urban planning, land management, and green infrastructure, engaging local and regional partners to enhance climate resilience and ensure a sustainable future.

NEXT STEPS

Regarding the **climate analysis**

- The project is complete for this initial phase, and no further actions are currently scheduled for this area.

Regarding the **heat risk analysis**

- A joint analysis of surface temperatures (LST) with different land uses will be conducted to identify which urban and territorial types contribute most to heat generation. This process aims to enable more targeted mitigation measures by prioritizing critical areas.

Regarding the **population vulnerability analysis**

- A composite vulnerability index will be developed, incorporating additional factors beyond age, such as per capita income, household income, and other relevant socioeconomic indicators. This index is intended to provide a detailed and accurate assessment of vulnerability at the local level. Public health data (e.g., hospitalizations, emergencies, or heat-related mortality) will be integrated to directly assess the health impact of extreme heat events on the population.

Regarding the **interest groups**

- A process will be initiated to contact all stakeholders previously identified and prioritized in this document. The purpose is to gather qualitative and contextual information to adjust and enhance the analysis results, ensuring alignment with the municipality's social and institutional context.

In addition to these analytical improvements, Phase 2 will include the following tasks:

- Identification and georeferencing of urban trees to generate an updated inventory of existing vegetation.
- Classification of tree species.
- Determination of structural vegetation variables such as cover, biomass, and leaf area.
- Assessment of Urban Green Infrastructure's capacity to improve municipal thermal and radiative comfort.
- Analysis of urban vegetation adaptability to climate change, including resilience and long-term management needs.
- Development of specific maps related to urban thermal exposure, including shading, pavement, permeability, and other heat accumulation factors.

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LUGIA PROJECT

RISK ANALYSIS OF HEAT WAVES AND THEIR IMPACT
ON VULNERABLE GROUPS IN HUÉRCAL-OVERA

Funded by the
European Union
NextGenerationEU